

ANALYSIS OF APPROACHES TO THE CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF ORGANIZING MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the conceptual foundations of management accounting. The approaches of economists who have studied the conceptual foundations of management accounting are described and analyzed. It also covers aspects such as the organization and maintenance of a management accounting system, the conceptual structure of management accounting.

The most important theoretical issue in developing the organizational and methodological foundations of management accounting is the study of its conceptual foundations. As a result of studying world practice, we came to the conclusion that there is no single conceptual model of management accounting. That is, for each country, economy, its sectors, and economic entities, there are management accounting systems that differ from each other in content and form, based on their own characteristics.

There is no consensus among scientists on the conceptual foundations of management accounting. For example, according to scientist J. Berfield, "The conceptual foundations of management accounting consist of: cost accounting, chart of accounts, reporting system and cost analysis". According to scientists I. Kabb, J. Innes and F. Mitchell, "the conceptual foundations of management accounting consist of: cost accounting, product costing, budgeting, reporting forms and forecasting".

According to foreign scientists Ch.T. Horngren and D. Foster, "The conceptual foundations of management accounting consist of: cost accounting, costing, planning, budgeting, strategic control, performance evaluation, forecasting". According to researcher S.Sh. Yuldashev, "The structural foundations of management accounting consist of: accounting, control, economic analysis and forecasting".

From the above ideas and considerations, it can be understood that there is no single accepted system of management accounting in all countries, economies, even among business entities. The main reasons for this are:

the absence of a single internationally accepted system of management accounting;

the fact that the organization and maintenance of management accounting is not required by law or regulations;

the fact that business entities in any country are not required to maintain management accounting;

the fact that management accounting is not required by higher organizations, etc.

The most important theoretical issue in developing the organizational and methodological foundations of management accounting is the study of its conceptual foundations.

So, as a result of a critical analysis of the opinions of scientists from the world and our republic on the conceptual structure of management accounting, it can be seen that there are different opinions on dividing it into components. Of course, there is also consensus on some aspects of this issue.

There are contradictions in the approaches of many economists to management accounting, that is, in explaining the essence of the conceptual basis of management accounting - cost accounting, costing, budgeting and analysis. Due to this situation, we have developed our proposal in order to form and develop the organization and maintenance of the management accounting system in our republic.

In our opinion, its composition includes: budgeting, planning, forecasting, working capital management, calculation and analysis of key performance indicators, categorization of costs based on management accounting requirements, chart of accounts for management accounting, coordination of cost groups in management and financial accounting, cost accounting, product costing, internal segment reporting system, procedure for coordinating management accounting records with financial accounting records, internal economic analysis, break-even point analysis, investment project analysis, transfer pricing formation.

The conceptual structure of management accounting is significant in that it pursues the following goals:

all costs of business entities are carried out through budgeting, which prevents various deviations;

categorization of costs based on management accounting requirements, which further increases the ability to coordinate the activities of profit, cost and responsibility centers;

provides the ability to calculate the cost of products using modern methods;

carrying out an analysis of the activities of business entities for the past and current periods creates the opportunity to make strategic decisions in the future, as well as to draw up a strategic forecast balance of business entities. The classification of costs based on the requirements of management accounting should be carried out according to profit, cost and responsibility centers and based on other management requirements. This will help us to identify the inclusion of costs in the specified centers by cost accounting items, their correct accounting, control and management analysis, and the application of necessary measures.

In general, the study of management accounting of costs will serve to reduce the cost of products, works and services in the future, and research in this area is of urgent importance.

Today, many regulatory and legal documents are being adopted in order to further develop the activities of business entities with various forms of ownership operating in our country. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023 on the “Uzbekistan-2030” Strategy, and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 on the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” serve as an important methodological basis for implementing the tasks set out in this area and implementing reforms in this area.

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